

**PROJECT FLOR (FAMILIARIZE, LEARN, OBTAIN, AND RELIVE):
THE DEVELOPED ARLING PANLIPUNAN 7 STRATEGIC
INTERVENTION MATERIALS**

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ABSTRACT

The main thrust of this study was to develop and validate Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan. This study followed the design and development research method. The respondents of the study, who were chosen through a simple stratified random sampling technique, were 78 Grade 7 learners from St. Vincent College of Cabuyao, and 16 Araling Panlipunan secondary teachers from St. Vincent College of Cabuyao and Liceo de Los Banos. Using a four-point Likert Scale, simple mean, and t-test for independent samples, the findings revealed that the developed of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials based on the assessment of the Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of objectives, content, language, and presentation were all highly valid. Meanwhile, the level of acceptability of the developed Strategic Intervention Materials of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan was also highly accepted based on the assessment of the Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of functionality, accuracy, suitability, and usability. There was a significant difference in the academic performance level of the learners comparing the mean scores of the learners during the pretest and posttest. It can be concluded that the developed strategic intervention materials of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan increased the acquisition of learning of Grade 7 learners based on the difference in their performance in the pretest and posttest.

Keywords: *developed, contextualized, instructional materials*

INTRODUCTION

History provides insight into the past, including triumphs, failures, and pivotal moments that shaped humanity. It taught students about various cultures, civilizations, and ideologies, promoting empathy and global awareness. It fostered critical thinking as students analyze events, identify patterns, and draw conclusions. Learning history taught students how to think critically, reason logically, and express their ideas coherently. It taught them about the context of current events and the interconnectedness of global affairs. Furthermore, history motivated students by demonstrating examples of human resilience, innovation, and achievement (Dan, 2022).

With reference to the article in MOOC.Org (2021), it was mentioned that learning about history aided students in understanding how historical occurrences shaped modern society. They learned about themselves and how they came to be, but they also gained the ability to avoid mistakes and forge better paths for their societies by using the lessons from the past. Events in the past uprooted families and groups, altering the demographics of areas and frequently igniting conflict. These occurrences produced political structures that have persisted for generations after their inception. And it all had an impact on every person alive today.

In the Philippines, the Araling Panlipunan class is considered a boring subject by the students due to the overwhelming information that learners need to absorb and remember.

Sometimes teachers need to do something excessive just to get the interest and attention of their students. In the new normal education, AP teachers opt to think of strategies that help them to make AP subjects as interesting as possible without compromising the quality of education that the students need to possess.

To strengthen the patriotism and nationalism of Filipino teachers and learners through learning, understanding, and appreciating history, the Department of Education initiated a program called *Balik Kasaysayan* Program. The main goal of the said project was to deepen awareness of the local (national and international if possible) history, culture, and arts that contribute to strengthening Filipino learners' patriotism and nationalism. With this program, DepEd achieved its vision where "We dream of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation" and therefore rewarding and making education redeeming. The expected outcome of the said project would be for schools to be able to produce functional teaching and learning resources and reference materials focusing on the history, culture, and arts that are based on primary sources and are accessible to all teachers and learners.

Since history is not integrated into Araling Panlipunan subject in the implementation of the K-to-12 Curriculum, various groups advocate for the reinstatement of Philippine history as a separate subject in grades K-12, rather than integrating it with

other subjects. In his write-up, veteran Filipino writer Isagani Cruz noted that "because the curriculum is so comprehensive, it is very difficult for a casual reader to identify the various strands that unify the content and performance standards of the different learning areas and grade levels" (Tumapon, 2022).

The reality that history is taken for granted in teaching Araling Panlipunan is the entry point of the researcher to conduct this study. Likewise, the learning competencies in Araling Panlipunan such as *Naipapaliwanag ang konsepto ng Asya tungo sa paghahating heograpiko*: Silangang Asya, TimogSilangang Asya, Timog-Asya, Kanlurang Asya, Hilagang Asya at Hilaga/ Gitnang Asya are needed to be enhanced, for the learners to be more prepared when the time comes that they encounter challenges in learning the subject, particularly in the higher level of Junior High School.

This study focused on the development of strategic intervention materials to scaffold the learning of Araling Panlipunan among Grade 7 learners. It was found out that St. Vincent College of Cabuyao lacked in the teaching and learning materials that were contextualized and localized. Through this initiative, strategic intervention materials that focused on contextualizing and localizing the lessons in Araling Panlipunan were provided.

Strategic Intervention Materials or SIM in the Philippine educational system, are instructional materials designed to reteach concepts or topics that the students believe they have not yet mastered. Guide cards, activity cards, assessment cards, enrichment cards, answer cards, and reference cards are the basic components of this. The mandate that no learner will be left behind is one of the Department of Education's goals. This makes sure that every student has an equal chance to succeed. to improve their schoolwork and gain proficiency in their least developed skills. Because of this, competency-based strategic intervention materials help learners develop their least-mastered skills, which is where they perform very poorly.

Research Questions

Purpose Statements

The purpose of this study was to develop and evaluate a strategic intervention material in Araling Panlipunan intended for Grade 7 learners. Furthermore, it aimed to:

1. Design and develop Strategic Intervention Materials in Araling Panlipunan 7 in consideration of the Most Essential Learning Competencies or MELCs.
2. Determine the validity and acceptability level of the Grade 7 Strategic Intervention Materials.
3. Identify if there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest in the use of Grade 7 Strategic Intervention Materials.

METHODOLOGY

The Design and Development Research Method was employed. Design and Development Research (DDR) provides an avenue for instructional designers to test theory, models, and frameworks, as well as validate practice. The usage, design, development, implementation, and assessment of products, tools, programs, and models employing instructional design models and frameworks is the emphasis of DDR.

According to Radcliffe (2023), the purpose of developmental research design was to determine how the researcher would collect data for the study. This design helped to focus on what changed and what remained constant while aging. It determined what information would be collected and how it would be obtained. The Design and Development Research approach was utilized in this study to improve the objects that were used and created. Furthermore, it was a way of creating or developing new resources as well as verifying current ones that helped students. The utilization of this design was appropriate for the conduct of this study since the study focused on developing a supplemental teaching material and further determining the effectiveness of the said material.

This research endeavor was conducted at St. Vincent College of Cabuyao since it was found that there was a need to develop supplemental material in teaching Araling Panlipunan Grade 7. Likewise, the academic performance of the learners in Araling Panlipunan was not that high the same as their engagement during class discussion.

Total enumeration was employed by the researcher for Araling Panlipunan teachers at St. Vincent College of Cabuyao and Liceo de Los Banos. Teachers who are teaching Araling Panlipunan served as respondents. Moreover, two sections with 78 learners from grade 7 served as learner participants. The learners were chosen through match-pairing. A matched pairs design is an experimental design that is used when there are just two treatment conditions in an experiment. The volunteers in the experiment are paired up based on some criteria that they "match" on, such as age or gender. The individuals are then randomly randomized to various treatments within each pair (Bobbitt, 2020).

The primary goal was to determine the effectiveness of the SIM in the academic performance of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

The study was comprised of two sections learner-respondents who were matched. Both of them took the pretest and post-test.

Table A
Respondents of the Study

Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Teachers	16	17.02
Students	78	82.73
Total	94	100.00

As shown in the table, the study had 94 respondents, 16 (17.02%) were teachers, and 78 (82.73) were students. These students were those who were enrolled at St. Vincent College of Cabuyao for the school year 2022-2023

Table B
Profile of the Teacher Interraters

Validators	Years in Handling AP 7	Educational Attainment
1	6	BSED
2	5	BSED
3	5	MAEd
4	6	BSED
5	7	MAEd
6	6	BSED
7	5	BSED
8	8	BSED
9	7	BSED
10	8	BSED
11	5	BSED
12	6	BSED
13	6	BSED
14	5	BSED
15	5	BSED
16	8	BSED

Another group of the study was the 16 teacher-validators that assessed the Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan materials. Most of them were BSED graduates, and two (2) of them were MAEd graduates. Three validators were teaching AP 7 for eight years, Two (2) validators have been teaching for seven (7) years, five (5) validators, for six (6) years, and six (6) validators, for five (5) years.

The study utilized an adopted instrument from Angay (2023) from her study. The research instrument was composed of two parts for experts' evaluation. Part 1 assessed the validity of the strategic intervention materials for Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan based on the objectives, content, language, and presentation. Part 2 assessed the acceptability of the strategic intervention materials for Araling Panlipunan in 4 terms of functionality,

accuracy, suitability, and usability with a four-point Likert scale will be applied and interpreted as follows:

**Level of Validity and Acceptability
Four-point Likert Scale**

	Scale	Level of Validity	Level of Acceptability
4	3.25-4.00	Highly Valid (HV)	Highly Accepted (HA)
3	2.50-3.24	Valid (V)	Accepted (A)
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Valid (SV)	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00-1.74	Not Valid (NV)	Not Acceptable (NA)

Moreover, the pretest and posttest for the first quarter were administered to the learner-respondents to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest. The results of the performance were interpreted using the levels of proficiency.

Levels of Proficiency

Level	Percentage
Outstanding	90-100
Very Satisfactory	85-89
Satisfactory	80-84
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79
Did not meet Expectations	Below 75

Source: DepEd Order No. 8, S. 2015 (Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program)

This study utilized an adopted survey questionnaire to validate the Developed Strategic Intervention Material in Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan. There were teacher raters who validated the instruments. These validators were master teachers and head teachers in Araling Panlipunan who were serving at public schools. To further check the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher asked the assistance of a statistician, and the questionnaire underwent a Reliability Test through Cronbach’s Alpha. The Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient result of the instrument was 0.940 for validity and 0.884 for acceptability (Frost, 2023).

First, the concerned parents, school principal, and district supervisor were given a letter of request. It was stipulated in the letter the goal of the study and the procedure for how the study would be conducted. Next, the intervention materials were evaluated by the teacher assessors, and with their recommendation, the materials were reproduced and given to the learners. That signaled the start of the intervention or experiment. Once the proposal and materials were approved by the school principal and district supervisor, orientation was done. There was a physical orientation conducted among the parents of the participants and this was done during the distribution of the materials. Since in-person

classes were being implemented, the researcher was provided printed intervention materials that learners can use. Lastly, the researcher got the data needed for the study, analysis, and interpretation of the data followed.

In the conduct of the study, the Data Privacy Act was strictly followed, and there was confidentiality particularly in the data of the learners as the main respondents.

This research followed the ethical requirements outlined in the DPA 2012 Manual when conducting the study. The importance and objectives of the study were conveyed to the participants. Full consent was solicited and obtained from the study's subjects. The information supplied by the participants was kept confidential, and their privacy was protected. The authors of the literature and research utilized to establish the rationale, and background of the investigation, and to support the study's conclusions were properly cited.

The following were the statistical treatments applied to the study using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

1. Mean and Likert scale were used to present the performance of the students in the pre and post-test.
2. Simple mean was used to determine the level of validity and acceptability of the developed strategic intervention materials for Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan.
3. T-test was used to identify if there was a significant difference in the performance of Grade 7 learners in their pretest and posttest.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Purpose Statement Number 1: Design and develop Strategic Intervention Materials in Araling Panlipunan 7.

The developed instructional materials in Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan were contextualized modules for the second quarter which discussed the basic concept and topics in Araling Panlipunan. In addition, the instructional material had information and practical exercises based on their everyday lives and current situation. Developed instructional modules made use of the IDEA format making it more interesting, easy to understand topics and application of the lesson to their day-to-day situation. Further, the Most Essential Learning Competencies were the bases in crafting strategic intervention materials. In crafting the materials, there was integration of localization and contextualization. Strategic Intervention Materials in Araling Panlipunan 7 in consideration of the Most Essential Learning Competencies or MELCs for the second quarter. Discusses the concept of Civilization and its characteristics, Comparing Ancient Asian Civilization (Sumer, Indus, China) and Assessing the influence of Asian thoughts on Social and Cultural Situation in Asia.

According to Paña's (2021) research, using the S.I.M. affected improving students' academic performance. Additionally, he suggested that conducting research would aid teachers in enhancing their students' learning.

Purpose Statement Number 2: Determine the validity and acceptability level of the Grade 7 Strategic Intervention Materials.

2.1 Content Validity

Table 1.1.1

Content Validity Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Objectives

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The objectives are clearly stated in behavioral form.	4.00	HV
2. The objectives are well-planned, formulated, and organized.	4.00	HV
3. The objectives stated are specific, measurable, and attainable.	3.94	HV
4. The objectives are relevant to the topics of each lesson of the worksheets.	3.94	HV
5. The objectives consider the needs of the students.	3.81	HV
General Assessment	3.90	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Objectives was **Highly Valid (3.90)**. “The objectives are clearly stated in behavioral form and well-planned, formulated, and organized” yielded the highest mean score of **4.00** interpreted as **Highly Valid**. On the other hand, “The objectives consider the needs of the students” received the lowest mean score of **3.81** interpreted as **Highly Valid**.

It implies that the objectives are relevant to the topic and are aligned with the most essential learning competencies. Learning objectives are used to direct learners as they go through the class and to evaluate their educational progress. In addition, exceptional objectives serve as a guide to learners upon examining the materials and getting ready for evaluations. Lastly, learning objectives are the most effective if they are specific, actionable, clearly stated, and measurable.

Contextualization was an instructional innovation that was developed at the turn of the 21st century. Montalbo and Villanueva (2020), defined contextualization as something related to the local environment, such as home, community, or workplace; contextualizing means creating a connection between the lessons taught in the classroom and what was happening in the real world outside. In this approach, the learners were given an “experience” of the lesson, not just pure thinking and imagination while seated in the classroom. In addition, Calimlim (2020) mentioned that contextualizing can significantly

support teaching and learning results. Thus, learners were expected to easily relate to the lesson, understand it better, and remember it more.

Table 1.1.2

Content Validity Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Content

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The content of each lesson is directly relevant to the defined objectives.	3.94	HV
2. The content of each lesson is simple and easy to understand.	4.00	HV
3. The topics of each lesson are fully discussed.	3.94	HV
4. The topics are supported by illustrative examples, and the practice tasks are suited to the level of the students.	3.94	HV
5. Each topic is given equal emphasis in the lesson	3.88	HV
General Assessment	3.94	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Content was **Highly Valid** (3.94). All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Highly Valid**. Moreover, the indicator “The content of each lesson is simple and easy to understand” had the highest computed mean of **4.00**, while the indicator “Each topic is given equal emphasis in the lesson” had the lowest computed mean of **3.88** which was also **Highly Valid**. It can be concluded that the Strategic Intervention Material in Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Content has high validity.

It implies that the content is relevant to the topic The content topic of each lesson is simple and easy to understand, the lessons are fully discussed, the topic is supported by illustrative examples, and the practice tasks are suited to the level of the students.

Marshall and Rossman (2018, as cited in Catuday, 2019) added that a valid development procedure should always be observed. Content validation was the most crucial and preliminary step towards material or instrument development. Content validation set the pace for succeeding validity and reliability measures. Careful planning, determination of objectives, and review of literature should be made at this point to be provided with comprehensive knowledge of the nature of the decision to be measured by the material or instrument.

Table 1.1.3

Content Validity Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Language

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The format/layout is well-organized, which makes the lessons more interesting.	4.00	HV
2. The language used is easy to understand.	4.00	HV
3. The language used is clear, concise, and motivating.	3.88	HV
4. The instructions in the worksheets are concise and easy to follow.	3.94	HV
General Assessment	3.92	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Language was **Highly Valid (3.92)**. Furthermore, the indicators “The format/layout is well-organized, which makes the lessons more interesting” and “The language used is easy to understand” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** interpreted as **Highly Valid**, while the indicator “The language used is clear, concise, and motivating” had the lowest computed mean of **3.88** interpreted as **Highly Valid**.

As stated in the study by Espiritu and Ogerio (2020), Araling Panlipunan was one of the subjects that learners took seriously during high school. Although Araling Panlipunan explored the daily activities of people and the right decision-making, when the lessons and activities were discussed in a foreign language, understanding the terms and meanings of words was quite difficult for junior high school learners. Thus, the emergence of a contextualized and localized curriculum was needed.

Table 1.1.4

Content Validity Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Presentations

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The topics are presented in a logical and sequential order.	3.94	HV
2. The lessons of the worksheets are presented in a unique and original form.	3.94	HV
3. The learning activities are presented clearly.	3.88	HV
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting to the students.	4.00	HV
5. Adequate examples are given to each topic.	3.88	HV
General Assessment	3.93	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Presentations were **Highly Valid (3.93)**. Moreover, the indicator “The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting to the students” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** while the indicators “The learning activities are presented clearly” and “Adequate examples are given to each topic” had the lowest computed mean of **3.88** interpreted as **Highly Valid**.

It affirms that the content and lessons of SIM are presented well. Moreover, the presentation is motivating for the learners because it is attractive and interesting. Additionally, the well-presented lessons and activities will make the learners engage more in the discussion while using the SIM.

In the study by Hasibuan (2019), he stated that the development and validation of learning materials should be practical and effective to improve the problem-solving skills and learning independence of the learners. Further, Lee (2021) emphasized that for instructional interventions to be effective, they must be: 1) intentional, focused on a specific challenge; 2) specific and formalized, addressing the learners' specific issues and concerns; and 3) flexible, applicable, and adaptable to the learners, given that each learner has unique needs and preferences. Based on the characteristics, it is possible to conclude that interventions should be developed with the goal of serving as a successful tool for improving learners' skills. As a result, teachers have a critical role in developing the interventions that will be implemented.

1.2 Acceptability

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Functionality were **Very Acceptable (3.94)**. Furthermore, the indicator “Worksheets serve their purpose” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** interpreted as **Very Acceptable**, while the indicator “Worksheets are self-instructed” had a computed mean of **3.88** which was still **Very Acceptable**.

Table 1.2.1

Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Functionality

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Worksheets are free of errors.	3.94	VA
2. Worksheets are self-instructed.	3.88	VA
3. Graphics and color increase the instructional value of the worksheets.	3.94	VA
4. Worksheets serve their purpose.	4.00	VA
5. Worksheets provide authorized easy access.	3.94	VA
General Assessment	3.94	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

The contextualized instructional material is clear, simple, and can be easily understood by the learners. Moreover, the information in the contextualized instructional materials stimulates learners' interest. Instructional materials are essential tools in learning and they also permit the learners to express their ideas with symbols, words, and images in manners that foster their capacities in thinking, talking, listening, composing, utilizing media, reading, solving, and innovation.

Instructional or learning materials as mentioned by Lewis (2018, as cited in Lorbis, 2019), referred to a selection of teaching materials that teachers used in teaching inside the classroom. These could be games, videos, flashcards, project supplies, and many more. Instructional materials were extremely fundamental in conveying directions since they helped the teaching and learning process. Moreover, students turned out to be more charmed and energized by the perception or assumption that they had materials to use to acquire knowledge. Educational material must also be aligned to the degree of progress of understanding to match the degree of cognizance.

Table 1.2.2

Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Araling Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Accuracy

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Worksheets contain correct information about the topic.	4.00	VA
2. Worksheets provide learners with the best choices for their answers.	3.94	VA
3. Choices reflect a certain degree of similarity in meaning but have distinct syntactic uses.	3.88	VA
General Assessment	3.94	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Accuracy were **Very Acceptable (3.94)**. Moreover, the indicator “Worksheets contain correct information about the topic” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** while the “Choices reflects a certain degree of similarity in meaning but have distinct syntactic uses” had the lowest computed mean **3.88**. Both were interpreted as **Very Acceptable**.

It reveals that the SIM has contents that are concise and accurate. The very goal of instructional materials is to provide information that is based on facts and that may allow learners to learn more about the subject matter. Likewise, the veracity of the material is a good component of its acceptability.

According to the article in Eduedify (2022), instructional materials were critical for effective teaching and learning. They can be used to help students learn new concepts and provide practice opportunities, as well as to support and supplement the lesson material. When selecting instructional materials, consider the students' ages and ability levels, as well as the lesson objectives. Teachers used instructional materials to pique their students' interest in learning. They included textbooks, workbooks, software, apps, games, videos, and other materials. When used correctly, instructional materials can accelerate students' acquisition of knowledge and skills.

Table 1.2.3

Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Suitability

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities of the learner.	3.94	VA
2. Activities are appropriate to the subject matter.	3.88	VA
3. Activities are relevant, interesting, and self - motivating to the learner.	3.94	VA
4. Use of enrichment activity is adaptable to classes with large number of learners.	3.88	VA
5. The language of the worksheets is within the vocabulary range of the target learners.	4.00	VA
General Assessment	3.93	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Suitability were **Very Acceptable (3.93)**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. Moreover, the indicator “The language of the worksheets is within the vocabulary range of the target learners” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** while the indicators “Activities are appropriate to the subject matter” and “Use of enrichment activity is adaptable to classes with large number of learners” had the lowest computed mean of **3.88**.

The Developed Contextualized Learning Activity Sheets in terms of Suitability are appropriate to the subject matter, and activities are relevant, interesting, and self-motivating to the learners. Moreover, the language is within the vocabulary range of learners. It only means that the activities in this instructional material are suited to the learners and provide teachable activities. The success of achieving what they mean to achieve in an instructional situation depends on the suitability of the instructional materials, adequacy, and effective utilization of the materials.

It was a greater method for finding new data to guarantee that the learning materials applied to what learners required. In addition, Mamais (2018) commented that instructional materials could increase the internal motivation of the learners to learn and sustain their interest. Instructional material made links that were valuable for the retention, inspiration, imagination, and innovation of learners.

Table 1.2.4

Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Usability

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The worksheets prepare the learners to think logically and critically.	3.94	VA
2. The concepts in the worksheets are simple and comprehensible.	4.00	VA
3. The worksheets enhance the learners' comprehension and reading skills.	3.88	VA
4. The worksheets provide the opportunity for the development of language skills.	3.94	VA
5. The learning contents provide adequate information on the topics presented.	3.88	VA
6. The worksheets encourage the learners to become actively involved in intellectual activities.	3.94	VA
7. Activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learning.	3.94	VA
8. As a whole, activities are teachable.	3.94	VA
General Assessment	3.93	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Usability were **Very Acceptable 3.93**. Furthermore, the indicator “The concepts in the worksheets are simple and comprehensible” had the highest computed mean of **4.00** interpreted as **Very Acceptable** while the indicators “The worksheets enhance the learners’ comprehension and reading skills” and “The learning contents provide adequate information on the topics presented” both had the lowest computed mean of **3.88** interpreted as **Very Acceptable**.

It can be concluded that the Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials in terms of Usability is very Acceptable. Additionally, localization helped learners foster the knowledge, abilities, and traits of good citizens by recognizing and following up on concerns and matters that involve the people in their community.

In the study by Macarubbo (2018), he said that the promotion of localized materials empowered the importance of neighborhood, social and socio-economic context. Therefore, the localization of material allowed learning to become meaningful and purposeful.

Purpose Statement Number 3: Identify if there is a significant difference between pretest and posttest in the use of Grade 7 Strategic Intervention Materials.

Table 2.1

Pretest Results of the Grade 7 Pretest Scores of Grade 7 Students in Using Strategic Intervention Materials

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	0	0.00
Very Satisfactory	1	1.28
Satisfactory	1	1.28
Fairly Satisfactory	24	30.77
Did not meet Expectations	52	66.67
Total	78.0	100.00
Average	72.88	

Legend : 90 - 100 Outstanding 85- 89 Very Satisfactory 80 - 84 Satisfactory
75 - 79 Fairly Satisfactory 74 below Did not Meet Expectations

The evaluation of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials yielded an average of 72.88 interpreted as **Did not Meet Expectations**. There were (0) Outstanding, 1 (1.28%) Very Satisfactory, 1 (1.28%), Satisfactory, 24 (30.77%) Fairly Satisfactory and 52 (66.67 %) Did not Meet Expectation.

It implies that students do not have enough knowledge yet in using strategic intervention materials. They may not have experienced such types of materials in their previous years. Their previous teachers might have used other types of intervention materials.

Furthermore, Lazo and De Guzman (2021) in their study suggested the consideration of the preparation of SIM for improving the advancement of desirable values and traits and free from biased content; more active learning activities aimed at increasing motivation and understanding and for the development of critical and higher-order thinking; and better efficiency of its assessment tools and techniques.

Table 2.2

Posttest Results of Grade 7 Students after Using Strategic Intervention Materials

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	0	0.00
Very Satisfactory	6	7.69
Satisfactory	11	14.10
Fairly Satisfactory	31	39.74
Did not meet Expectations	30	38.46
Total	78	100.00

Legend : 90 - 100 Outstanding 85- 89 Very Satisfactory 80 - 84 Satisfactory
 75 - 79 Fairly Satisfactory 74 below Did not meet expectations

The evaluation of Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials yielded an average of 78 interpreted as Fairly Satisfactory. There were (0) Outstanding, 6 (7.69%) Very Satisfactory, 11 (14.10%), Satisfactory, 31 (39.74%) Fairly Satisfactory and 30 (38.46%) Did not meet expectations.

It implies that the teacher used SIM. However, she utilized it for only two weeks, hence, her expectation of a better result did not happen.

In the study conducted by Bonitez (2021), the results showed that using SIM significantly improved the respondents' performance levels. This demonstrated how using SIM had a significant impact on how well students understood the lesson. To facilitate learning and enhance student performance, SIM should be modified as an "aid" for instructional materials. Teachers can re-teach the concepts and skills using the researcher's SIM. It was strongly advised that SIM be implemented and developed to improve student learning across the board, not just in the Philippines.

Table 2.3

Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Summary among the Grade 7 using the SIM

Indicators	Test	Paired Differences			P value	Remarks	Decision
		Mean	SD	T			
Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials	Pre & Post	- 3.23	2.66	-10.71	.000	Significant	Reject ho

There was a significant difference between the performance of the students in the pretest and posttest. The probability value was .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. The improvement in the posttest results is attributed to the utilization of the Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention Materials.

The improvement in the post-test results is attributed to the utilization of the grade 7 Araling Panlipunan Strategic Intervention materials.

According to Sta. Rosa (2021), S.I.M. used among Araling Panlipunan students in Junior High School aided in improving and developing mastery skills and addressing the varied learning progress of each student. Furthermore, it met the needs of the students in terms of least-mastered competencies and aided teachers in making teaching easier.

Conclusions

Purpose of Strategic Intervention Materials

Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) is used in remedial sessions to focus on developing the learners' least mastered skills. It is a learning tool that assists students in mastering competency-based abilities that they may not have been able to develop in a traditional classroom setting.

Araling Panlipunan 7
Quarter 2
Week 1

**PAGSUSURI SA KATANGIAN AT
KAHALAGAHAN NG KABIHASNAN**

Layunin:

1. Makapagbibigay ng konseptong naglalarawan at tumutukoy sa kabihasan.
2. Naipapahayag ang naglalarawan sa kabihasan.

Guide Card 1

Konsepto ng Kabihasanan

Orihinal na tumutukoy sa kahulugan ng "sibilisasyon" o "paninirahan sa lungsod"

Isang maunlad na kalagayan ng mga tao sa isang lipunan na pinangangasiwaan ng isang sistematikong pamamahala at may maunlad na ekonomiya or kalakalan

Ang unang kabihasanan ay nalinang sa mga ilog-lambak

Sa Asya, ang mga ilog-lambak ng Tigris, Euphrates, Huang He at Indus Basin ay ang mga lugar na pinagmulan ng mga sinaunang kabihasanan sa mundo

Sa isang kabihasanan, makikita ang isang maunlad na uri ng pamumuhay ng mga tao na may ugnayan sa iba't ibang larangan ng panlipunang pamumuhay

Mayroon silang sistema ng pamamahala, kultura, lalakalan, at relihiyon

Guide Card 2

Pinagmulan ng Sinaunang Kabihasanan sa Mundo

Ilog ng Tigris at Euphrates

Ilog ng Indus

Ilog ng Huang He

Ang sibilisasyon ay tumutukoy sa isang lungsod, samantalang ang kabihasanan ay may kaugnayan sa pagiging bihasa o eksperto sa pamumuhay ng mga tao.

Sinasabi na ang sibilisasyon at kabihasanan ay nagaganap kapag ang mga tao ay nagsisimulang matuto ng kanilang pagsulat at pagbasa na nakapagpapatalas ng kanilang talino at humuhubog sa kanilang kakayahang mamuhay bilang isang pamayanan. Kaakibat ng pagyabong ng kanilang talino at kakayanan at pag unlad ng kanilang pagkatao.

Activity Card 1

Mula sa iyong natutuhan sa kabilang pahina, magbigay ng limang (5) konseptong naglalarawan sa isang kabihasanan.

Kabihasanan

Activity Card 2

Tukuyin kung anong katangian ang binibigyang kahulugan ng mga pangungusap sa loob ng kahon:

Naisasalin ang kanilang karunungan at natutunan sa isa paglipas ng panahon para sa susunod na henerasyon.

Natututunang maiangkop ang kanilang sarili at gawain na naaayon sa hinihinging pagkakataon.

Nagkakaroon ng maayos na pamamalakad sa bawat paggawa at pakikipag-ugnayan ng mga tao sa isa't-isa.

Nagiging sandigan ng pag-unlad ng lipunan upang marating ang estado ng pagiging kabihasan.

Guide Card 3

Matatag na Pamahalaang may Maunlad na Batas at Alituntunin

Dalubhasang Manggagawa

Maunlad na Kaisipan

May Sistema ng Pagtatala

Katangian ng Kabihasan

Enrichment Card 1

Base sa iyong mga karaniwang nararanasan sa kasalukuyan at sa mga natutuhan mo tungkol sa konsepto at katangian ng kabihasan, magbigay ng pagpapakahulugan sa mga letrang bumubuo sa salitang kabihasan.

K Kaisipan ay yumayabong ayon sa nararanasan .
A _____
B _____
I _____
H _____
A _____
S _____
N _____
A _____
N _____

Assessment Card 1

Basahing mabuti ang mga pangungusap. Isulat ang salitang TAMA kung wasto ang ipinapahayag ng pangungusap at MALI kung di-wasto.

- _____ 1. Sa isang kabihasan, makikita ang isang progresibong uri ng pamumuhay ng mga tao na may ugnayan sa iba't ibang larangan ng panlipunang pamumuhay.
- _____ 2. Ang ilog Jordan ay isa sa mga pangunahing ilog na pinagsimulaan ng isang kabihasan.
- _____ 3. Habang umuunlad ang pamumuhay ng mga tao, yumayabong din ang kanilang kaisipan.
- _____ 4. Sa pamamagitan ng pagsulat ng kanilang kaalaman, nananatiling bahagi ng kanilang kabihasan ang kanilang natutuhan, kasaysayan at mga napagtagumpayan ng kanilang mamamayan.
- _____ 5. Ang kabihasan ay tumutukoy sa isang lungsod, samantalang ang sibilisasyon ay may kaugnayan sa pagiging bihasa o eksperto sa pamumuhay ng mga tao.

Araling Panlipunan 7 *Quarter 2* *Week 2-3*

SINAUNANG KABIHASNAN SA ASYA: SUMER, INDUS, AT TSINA

Layunin:

1. Napaghahambing at naitatala ang mga katangiang pisikal ng mga sinaunang kabihasan sa Asya.
2. Naibibigay ang pagbabago at pag-unlad ng pamumuhay ng kabihasang umunlad sa Asya.

Guide Card

*Sinaunang Kabihasan sa Asya:
Sumer, Indus at Tsina (Shang)*

Guide Card KABIHASNANG SUMER

(3500 BCE - 3000 BCE)

KABIHASNANG SUMER

Ang Mesopotamia ang kinilala bilang *cradle of civilization* dahil dito umuhong ang unang sibilisadong lipunan ng tao.

Matatagpuan ang Mesopotamia sa Gitnang Silangan na tinawag na *Fertile Crescent* kung saan matatagpuan ang kambalilog na *Tigris* at *Euphrates*.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

Pagtatanim, pangangalakal, pangangaso at pag-aalaga ng hayop ang pangunahing hanapbuhay ng mga Sumerian.

Sistemang Panrelihiyon

Ang pinakamalaking gusali sa Sumer ay ang templo na tinatawag na *Ziggurat*.
Pinamunuan ng mga haring pari ang mga lungsod dito.

Mga Ambag ng Sumerian

Isa sa mga ambag ng mga Sumerian ay ang sistema ng pagsulat na tinawag na *cuneiform* kung saan naitala ng mga *scribe* sa mga *clay tablet* ang mga mahahalagang pangayaring naganap.

Iba pang kontibusyon

- Epic of Gilgamesh
- Araro at mga kariton na may gulong
- Palayok
- Perang pilak
- Lunar calendar
- Decimal system

KABIHASNANG INDUS

Sa Timog Asya makikita ang lambak-ilog ng Indus at Ganges. Dito umuhong ang kabihasnang Indus.

Guide Card KABIHASNANG INDUS

(2500 BCE - 1600 BCE)

KABIHASNANG INDUS

Naging mahiwaga ang paglaho ng kabihasnang Indus. May paliwanag ang iskolar dito. Ayon sa kanilang teorya:

1. Kalamidad
2. Pananakop

Ngunit walalang matibay na ebidensyang naitipika sa mga paliwanag na ito.

Mga Ambag

Ang mga Dravidian ay gumamit ng mga pictogram bilang sistema ng pagsulat, ngunit hanggang ngayon ay wala pang nakakalam kung ano ang kahulugan ng mga ito.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

May dalawang importanteng lungsod ang umuhong dito, ang *Harappa* at *Mohenjo-Daro*. Planado at organisado ang mga lungsod na ito na ipinakit sa mga lansangang nakadisensyo sa kuwadrado (grid-patterned) at pare-pareho ang sukat ng bloke ng kabahayan.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

- ✓ Pinilagay na ang mga Dravidian ang buntao ng kabihasnang Indus.
- ✓ Pinamunuan ang kabihasnang ito ng mga haring pari.
- ✓ Pagsasaka ang ikinabuhay ng mga tao dito.
- ✓ Narami rin silang makipag-kalakalan sa mga karatig lungsod.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

Mohenjo-Daro at Harappa

Sistemang Panrelihiyon

Sinasamba ng mga Dravidian ang maraming Diyos na sumisimbolo sa pwersa ng kalikasan.

KABIHASNANG SHANG

Ito ang kabihasnang nagsimula sa lambak ng Huang Ho sa China na tinawag ding *Yellow River* dahil pagkatapos ng pagbaha ang tubig nito ay nag-iwan ng *loess* o dilaw na lupa na nagsisilbing pataba sa lupaing agrikultural na malapit dito.

Mga Ambag

Calligraphy ang sistema ng kanilang pagsulat na nag-iilang mga pagtatawag sa mga Tao. Gamit na simbolo ng pagsulat ang mga oracle bone.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

Ang Lungshan ay naging transisyong tungo sa Kabihasnang Shang. May hinalang may naunang dinastiya na natatag dito, ang Xia subalit wala itong matibay na basehan ebidensyang arkeolohikal.

Sistemang Pampulitika at Pang-ekonomiya

May mga pamayanan ng umuhong dito bago ang Shang. Ito ang kalinangan ng *Yanshao* (3000 BCE - 1500 BCE) at *Lungshan* (2500 BCE - 2000 BCE). Pagtatawag ang pangunahing gawain sa panahong ito.

Activity Card

Itala ang mga katangiang pisikal ng mga sumusunod na sinaunang Kabihasnang sa Asya.

Kabihasnang Sumer

Kabihasnang Indus

Kabihasnang Shang

Assessment Card

Punan ang mga hinihinging impormasyon tungkol sa naging pagbabago at pag-unlad ng pamumuhay ng mga kabihasnang umunlad sa Asya.

Lugar na Pinagmulan ng Kabihasnang	Kabihasnang Umusbong	Mga Unang Pamayanang Umusbong	Sistema ng Pagsulat
Mesopotamia			
Indus Valley			
China			

Enrichment Card

Itala ang mga impormasyong pagkakatulad at pagkakaiba ng mga kabihasnang sa loob ng Venn Diagram.

Araling Panlipunan 7
Quarter 2
Week 4

**PAGSUSURI SA KAISIPANG ASYANO SA
IMPLUWENSIYA NITO LIPUNAN AT
KULTURA**

Layunin:

1. Natataya ang impluwensya ng mga kaisipang Asyano sa kalagayang panlipunan at kultura sa Asya.
2. Naibibigay ang katangiang pagkakakilanlan ng kaisipang Asyano.

Guide Card

Sinocentrism ng China

- Ang kabihasnang Tsino ay isa sa mga pinagmulan ng mga kaisipang Asyano lalo na sa larangan ng pilosopiya, pamamahala at imbensiyon.
- Itinuturing ng mga Tsino ang kanilang bansa bilang "Gitnang Kaharian" o "Zongguo" na ang ibig ipakahulugan ay ang Tsina ang sentro ng daigdig.
- Naniniwala rin sila na ang kanilang kultura at lipunan ay namumukodtangi sa lahat kung kayat ang tingin nila sa ibang lahi sa daigdig ay mga barbaro.
- Hindi maaring palitan ang lahi o pamilyang pinagmulan ng kanilang pinuno o Emperor.
- Hindi rin sila maaaring tanggalan ng tungkulin sa pamumuno ng bansa dahil sa pinaniniwalaang Divine Origin ng kanilang pamilya.
- Ang kanilang Emperor ay may "mandate of heaven" na nagiging basehan ng pagpapalit ng dinastiya sa Tsina.

Guide Card

Divine Origin ng Emperor sa Japan

Ayon sa tala sa Kojiki noong 712 CE, ang Japan ay nabuo sa pagtatalik ng diyos na si Izanagi at diyosa na si Izanami. Samantalang sa pagbubukas ng kaliwang mata ni Izanami nanggaling ang araw na kinilala ng mga Hapones na diyos na si Amaterasu Omikami. Si Amaterasu ay may apo na nanggangalang Ninigi na nanirahan sa Kyushu.

Ayon sa tradisyon, itong si Ninigi-no-Mikoto ay may kaapu-apuhan na ang pangalan ay Jimmu Tenno na naging kauna-unahang Emperor ng Japan. Magmula noon, sa lahi ng Tenno nanggagaling ang mga susunod na emperor ng Japan.

Dahil dito, ang kanilang Emperor ay hindi maaaring palitan ang lahing pagmumulan ng pinuno o kaya ay tanggalan ng tungkulin sa pamumuno ng bansa, sa pagkat naniniwala sila na may Divine Origin ang kanilang pinuno. Bagamat sa kasalukuyan hindi na itinuturing ng mga Hapones ang kanilang Emperor bilang diyos, nananatiling mataas ang pagtingin nila sa kanilang emperador.

Activity Card

Isulat sa loob ng kahon kung anong kaisipang Asyano ang tinutukoy at batayan ng pinagmulan ng kaisipang ito.

Kaisipang Asyano

China

Japan

India

Assessment Card

Tukuyin at isulat ang mga katangiang pagkakakilanlan ng bawat kaisipang Asyano.

Kaisipang Asyano	Katangian/Pagkakakilanlan
Sinocentrism	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____
Divine Origin	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____
Devaraja	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____
Cakravartin	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____

Enrichment Card

Ibigay ang hinihingi.

Tatlong (3) konsepto na natutunan ko mula sa Aralin:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Dalawang (2) mahalagang bagay na ayaw kong makalimutan mula sa Aralin:

1. _____
2. _____

Isang (1) impormasyon na gusto kong subukan mula sa aking natutunan sa Araling ito:

1. _____

Assessment Card

Isulat ang mga tungkuling nakaatas sa mga pinuno na nakasulat sa kahon. Gamitin ang tsart sa ibaba sa pagsagot.

Uri ng Pinuno	Tungkulin ng Sinaunang Namumuno
Emperor ng China	
Emperor ng Japan	
Cakravartin	

Enrichment Card

Ibigay ang hinihingi.

Tatlong (3) konsepto na natutunan ko mula sa Aralin:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Dalawang (2) mahahalagang bagay na ayaw kong makalimutan mula sa Aralin:

1. _____
2. _____

Isang (1) impormasyon na gusto kong subukan mula sa aking natutunan sa Araling ito:

1. _____

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the conduct of the study, the Data Privacy Act was strictly followed, and there was confidentiality particularly in the data of the learners as the main respondents. This research followed the ethical requirements outlined in the DPA 2012 Manual when conducting the study. The importance and objectives of the study were conveyed to the participants. Full consent was solicited and obtained from the study's subjects. The information supplied by the participants was kept confidential, and their privacy was protected. The authors of the literature and research utilized to establish the rationale, and background of the investigation, and to support the study's conclusions were properly cited.

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